

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2
0
2
5

No

1

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 838 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 7-yanvarda ruxsat etildi.*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayeich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodzjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

“Yashil” makon “yashil” iqtisodiyot farovonligimiz garovi.....	20
Muhiddin Kalonov	
Xufyona iqtisodiyot va uni qisqartirishning ilmiy tadqiqotlardagi talqinining ilmiy tahlili.....	23
Raxmanov Laziz Erkabaevich	
O‘zbekistonda yashil loyihalarni moliyalashtirish amaliyoti tahlili.....	28
Bakirov Sanjar Davlatovich	
Respublika iqtisodiyotida oilaviy korxonalarining eksport faoliyati tahlili.....	35
Jurayev Navruz Jurayevich	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan kredit liniyalarini samarali boshqarish mexanizmlari.....	40
Toshboyev Sherzod Turdaliyevich	
Innovatsion faoliyatda yashil kimyoning strategik o‘rni: global va mahalliy yondashuvlar.....	45
Nazarova Latofat Toirjon qizi	
Barqaror iqtisodiy o‘shishni ta’minlashda tabiiy kapitalning ahamiyati.....	49
Urunbayev Saparbek Samatovich	
Sug‘urta kompaniyalari biznes modeli.....	54
Qarshiyev Otabek Abdullayevich	
Страхование различных рисков проектного финансирования.....	59
Гулираъно Носирова Абдулазиз кизи	
“Yashil” texnologiyalar – yashil iqtisodiyotning bo‘g‘ini sifatida.....	63
Boboqulov Sanjar Baxronkulovich, Qurbonov Tolmasjon Namoz o‘g‘li, Shodiyev Fazliddin Qalandar o‘g‘li	
Iste‘mol soliqlarining tovar va xizmatlar bahosiga ta‘sirini baholash.....	70
Ergashev I. O.	
Экологические аспекты “зелёной экономики” в стратегии устойчивого развития Узбекистана.....	73
Кучаров Абдор Сабиринович, Джумабаева Дилобар Асатиллаевна, Шомалиева Мукаддасхон Мирсаидовна	
O‘zbekistonda pensiya tizimini takomillashtirish.....	78
Tursunov Jaxongir Pulatovich	
Yoshlarda tadbirkorlik qobiliyatini shakllantirish va yoshlar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish modellari.....	84
Raxmatullayeva Feruza Azimovna	
Korxonalar import operatsiyalarida moliyaviy munosabatlar nazariy tahlili.....	90
Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
Hududlararo iqtisodiy mutanosibliklarni aniqlash uslubiyoti.....	95
Murtazayev Isabek Bazarbayevich	
“MUQADDAM” MCHJ kalava ip ishlab chiqarish korxonasida marketing strategiyasini takomillashtirish yo‘llari.....	103
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Kurbonboyeva Sevinch Asliddinovna	
O‘zbekistonda davlat mulkini xususiyashtirish jarayonlari va ularning iqtisodiy rivojlanishga ta‘siri.....	109
Shadmanov Erkin Sherkulovich, Turkmanov Azam Saydullaevich	
Особенности современных методов оценки эффективности деятельности промышленных предприятий.....	114
Матчанов Азамат Абатович	
Kichik biznes subyektlari tomonidan mahalliyashtirish asosida mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishni tashkil etishda davlat dasturlarining ahamiyati.....	121
Mirzabaev Xusniddin Muxamadjonovich	
Davlat statistikasini xalqaro statistika standartlar asosida innovatsion rivojlantirish yo‘llari.....	128
T.P. Jemuratov	
Tadbirkorlikni boshqarishda sun‘iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanish.....	134
Sobirjonov Sanjar Sobirjonovich, G‘ulomova Iroda Jahongir qizi	

Davlat-xususiy sheriklik: mohiyati, funksiyalari va jahon amaliyoti	139
Ataniyazova Maksuda Baltabayevna	
Qurilish korxonalarida sanoat mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	144
Amirov Zubaydulla Toir o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda bandlikni tartibga solishda tadbirkorlikning ahamiyati	148
Ismailov Azizbek	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash davrida bandlik siyosati.....	151
Mardanaqulov To'liqin	
Tadbirkorlikning ijtimoiy funksiyasini namoyon bo'lishi.....	154
Xalilov Muxiddin Shakirovich	
Ijtimoiy dasturlarni amalga oshirishda davlat ijtimoiy buyurtmasining ahamiyati	158
Xusanov Otabek Nishonovich	
Shaxsiy sug'urtaning iqtisodiy mohiyati va tashkil etish prinsiplari.....	163
Bazarov Zakir Xonqulovich	
Moliyaviy munosabatlarda benefitsiar mulkdorlarning iqtisodiy faoliyati va ularga xizmat ko'rsatish tizimi tahlili	168
Ochilov Farhod Malikovich	
Оптимизация стратегий коммерциализации инновационных проектов в организациях	174
Бобокулов Шохрух	
Sog'lom ovqatlanish umumiy ovqatlanish sohasini barqaror rivojlantirishning asosi sifatida	178
Raximova Dilorom Sulaymonovna	
"Yashil" iqtisodiyotga o'tishda davlatning roli.....	184
Ulug'murodova Feruza Mardon qizi, R.A. Saydaqulov	
Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda "Yashil" iqtisodiyotga o'tishning imkoniyatlari va muammolari.....	190
Jumaniyazov Nodirbek Odilbek o'g'li	
Aksiz solig'ining davlat budjetini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati va zarurati: xalqaro va mahalliy tajriba	195
Kabirov Abdulla Maxmutovich	
Tijorat banklari aktivlari samaradorligini oshirish.....	201
Xojibekova Zilola Shavkat qizi	
Davlat budjeti daromadlarini shakllantirish bo'yicha xorij tajribalari	206
Kudaybergenova Guzal	
Развитие международного рынка капитала	216
Срождиддинова Зарина Хайриддиновна, Абдираманова Мадина Куанишбаевна	
Финансовый анализ нефтесервисной компании АО «МАХСУСЭНЕРГОГАЗ»	228
Файзиев Умуркул Шухратович	
Tijorat banklarida raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish bilan bog'liq muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari.....	236
Xudayarov Oybek Odilovich	
Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarining tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	242
Seytnazarov Berdibek Ametbekovich	
Surxondaryo viloyatida yashil iqtisodiyotni amaliyotga tatbiq etishning hozirgi holati	246
Oybek Ruziyev Abdumuminovich, Qosimov Akmal, Mamatov Sardor Ilyosovich	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirish va aholi bandligini ta'minlashda tadbirkorlik faoliyatining o'rni	251
Saparov Ismat Chorshanbiyevich	
Leveraging ICT and mobile connectivity for economic growth: an empirical study on the role of internet usage and corruption control	256
G'ofirova Gulmira G'anisherovna, Rajabova Malika Nuriddin qizi, Qalandarov Sarvar Zafar o'g'li	
Sanoatda oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari xavfsizligini ta'minlash va sertifikatlashtirish mexanizmini takomillashtirish	266
Mahamatova Maftuna	
Soliq tizimida elektron hujjat aylanishining soliq ma'murchiligiga ta'siri	273
Abdullaev Shahbozbek Nodirsho o'g'li	
Respublikamizdagi sanoat korxonalarining rivojlanishini ko'p omilli tahlillari	283
Jalolov Ilhomjon Isomiddinovich	

Organizational economic mechanisms of the tourist services market in the republic of Karakalpakstan.....	290
Ochilova Ozoda Toshquvatovna	
Qishloq hududlarini iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari	295
Toyirov Alijon Yodgor o'g'li, Sadullayev Oybek Turdiali o'g'li, Orziqulov Oybek A'zamjon o'g'li	
Ta'lim turizmi va madaniy meros: O'zbekiston Respublikasida tutgan o'rni.....	300
Qutlimurotov Fayzullo Sadulayevich	
Глэмпинг: особенности и перспективы развития в Республике Узбекистан.....	304
Гуломова Мухлиса Нурулла кизи, Муллагалиева Зарина Рамиловна, Исамиддинова Диёра Нодиржон кизи	
Improving the practice of crediting business entities by commercial banks	309
Jabbarov Alisher Kayimovich	
O'zbekistonda eksport-import operatsiyalarini sug'urtalashning rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	314
Adilova Gulnur Djurabayevna	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirishda xizmatlar sohasining o'rni	319
Mirzaev Qulmamat Djonuzokovich, Saparov Murod Irgashovich	
Ishchi kuchi migratsiyasini tartibga solishga yondashuvlar	323
Xamidov Elyorjon Tursunali o'g'li	
Kichik biznes sohasiga investitsiyalarni jalb etish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	329
Bolliyev Shamsiddin Tursunmamatovich	
Mahalliy ishlab chiqarish korxonalari raqobatbardoshligini baholashning zamonaviy yondashuvlari, mezonlari va usullari	335
Buriyev Ubaydulla Bozor o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarida kredit amaliyotini takomillashtirish istiqbollari	338
Xolmatov Mirodil Nurmamat o'g'li	
The role of agrobusiness in the development of society and its opportunities.....	343
D. Dzhurayeva, Rakhmonov Rustam	
Ichki audit samaradorligini baholashga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar va ko'rsatkichlar tahlili	349
B.Y.Maxsudov, I.G'.Isroilov	
Qurilish materiallari sanoatida innovatsion samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlari	353
Yuldasheva Kamola Miraliyevna	
Эффективная политика регулирования занятости как фактор сокращения бедности населения	357
Шаюсупова Наргиза Тургуновна	
Global iqtisodiy barqarorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlashda mintaqaviy savdo kelishuvlarining o'rni	365
Toyirov Alijon Yodgor o'g'li, Egamberdiyev Nurmuhammad Otabek o'g'li	
Moliyaviy salohiyatni baholash metodologiyasini shakllanishida makroiqtisodiy indikatorlarning ahamiyatliligi	370
Buranova Lola Vakhobovna	
Navoiy viloyatida sanoat tarmog'i rivojlanishi tahlili.....	379
Baqoyev Husan Nuriddinovich	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarining innovasion faoliyatini moliyalashtirishning davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlari.....	383
Shomansurova Zilola Abduvaxitovna	
Internet – iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning muhim kaliti.....	391
Bo'tayeva Sabina Xoliyorovna	
Chet mamlakatlarida soliq qarzlari undirish mexanizmini milliy soliq tizimiga moslashtirish masalalari	396
Yuldashev Dilshod Rustamovich	
O'zbekistonda hududiy turizmni barqaror rivojlantirishda ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy hamda hukumat strategiyalarining roli va ta'siri.....	402
Yorqulov Muhammadmurod Axmad o'g'li	
Mintaqaning barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishida pochta aloqasi xizmatlarining tutgan o'rni (Xorazm viloyati misolida).....	408
Palvanbayev Umidbek O'ktam o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda islom bank xizmatlarini joriy etish istiqbollari	412
Dodieva Umida Fozil qizi	

Mehnat bozorini takomillashtirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning amaliy jihatlari	416
Maxammadiyev M.M.	
Davlat ulushiga ega bo'lgan yirik soliq to'lovchilar ma'murchiligini takomillashtirish yo'llari	421
Erkaboev Nuriddin Axmadjonovich	
To'qimachilik sanoatida mahsulot tannarxini kamaytirishning iqtisodiy ahamiyati va zaruriyati.....	429
Gaybullayeva Gulbaxor Maxmudovna	
Turizm va xizmatlar sohasini raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari.....	432
Asadov Baxshullo Xasanboy o'g'li	
2025-yilda soliq ma'murchiligi bo'yicha amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar	437
Normurzaev Umid Xolmurzaevich	
Aholi daromadlari manbalarining shakllanish xususiyatlari.....	445
Shohruh Toshtemirov	
O'zbekistonda xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirish orqali iqtisodiy o'sishga erishish istiqbollari.....	450
Usmonov Navruzbek Erkin o'g'li, Norqobilov Hamza Eshdovlat o'g'li	
Об оценке налоговой нагрузки, могущей отразить финансовое обеспечение потребности бюджета	459
Зайналов Джахонгир Расулович	
Termiz temir yo'l uzelinig yuk aylanmasi hajmi tahlili	466
Dilfuza Shakarova Ruzimuratovna	
Jahon global raqobat muhitida mavjud xom-ashyo va resurslarini strategik muammolari.....	472
Mamatkulov Akram Xalmurodovich	
Зарубежный опыт повышения конкурентоспособности текстильной промышленности на основе ИКТ	476
Матчанова Феруза Абадовна	
Построение интегрированной системы управления затратами предприятий.....	482
Алиева С.С.	
Развитие корпоративного управления в Узбекистане на основе современных мировых стандартов	487
Ибрагимова Саодат Абдумуниновна, Абдулазизов Ферузбек Дилшодбек Ўғли	
Foyda solig'ini davlat budjetidagi ahamiyati.....	494
Ibragimov Xamidbek Jumaniyazovich	
Aholi turmush farovonligi va barqaror rivojlanish o'rtasidagi munosabatlar	501
Sharofiddin Ismatov Asatulloevich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotning sohalari, xususiyatlari va asosiy elementlari	506
Raxmatullayev Lazizbek Ruslanovich, Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
Цифровизация в банковской сфере Республики Узбекистан	510
Салимова Зиёда Рустамжон кизи	
Digital inclusion and rural development: the socio-economic and cultural impact of internet connectivity	515
Elyor Urozaliev	
Моделирование процесса оптимального распределения пищевых ресурсов при повышении эффективности производства мясных продуктов в условиях цифровой экономики	525
Рахимбердиев Кувончбек Бахтиёрович, Тошпулов Бекзод Султонмуродович	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalarning innovatsion shakllarini rivojlantirishning hozirgi tendensiyalari (Koreya misolida)	530
Achilova Shirin Shavkat qizi	
Iqtisodiy sikllarni aniqlash metodologiyasiga yondashuvlar	536
Jabborov Kamoliddin Yo'ldoshevich	
Davlat sektorida ichki auditni takomillashtirish masalalari	543
Gulmatov Jamoliddin Raxmatullaevich	
Islomiy banklarning iqtisodiy barqarorlikka qo'shgan hissasi va ular orqali amalga oshiriladigan iqtisodiy islohotlar	548
Pulatova Adolat Djaxangirshyevna	

Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tijorat banklari chakana xizmatlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	553
Boymaxmadov Alisher Xoliyor o'g'li	
Комплаинс в системе «зеленой экономики»: международный опыт	560
Юнусова Римма Рахманбердиевна	
«Зеленая экономика» Республики Узбекистан в условиях трансформации угроз экономической безопасности	567
Пантин Роман Владимирович	
Правовые основы и особенности организации формирования доходов местных бюджетов и их источников в узбекской практике	575
Бабаджанова Лола Шопулатовна	
O'zbekiston turizm mintaqalarining etnografik resurslar salohiyatini baholash ko'rsatkichlari tahlili	583
Dilyor Zafarovich Hakimov	
Xizmatlar sohasining rivojlanishi sharoitida samarqand viloyatida ijara bozorining o'sish dinamikasi va kelajak prognozlarini.....	592
Oybek Juliboy o'g'li	
The role of operational CRM systems in sales departments	596
Aziza Egamnazarova, Maftuna Shoyzoqova, Gaffarova Sarvinoz Muzaffar qizi, Turaeva Gulizaxro	
O'zbekistonda davlat moliyaviy nazoratining yangi arxitekturasini shakllantirish yo'nalishlari.....	601
Jabborov Azamat Alijonovich	
Долгосрочная стратегия повышения эффективности социальных сетей в сфере туризма	607
Касимова Зилола Гуламиддиновна	
Глобальные экологические инициативы и их влияние на международную экономику	615
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович	
Ko'chmas mulk qiymatini baholashda axborotlar tizimini shakllantirish	621
Ishonqulov Nizamjon Fayzullaevich	
Innovatsion salohiyatni oshirish orqali tijorat banklari aktivlari sifatini yaxshilash yo'llari	628
Ruziyev Baxtiyor Salimboyevich	
Soliq qarzdorlikni kamaytirishdagi mavjud muammolar	634
Maxmadustov Jalol Maxmadustovich	
O'zbekistonda ta'lim turizmini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	644
Azimova Vazira Oqiljonovna	
“Yashil” iqtisodiyotni rivojlanish uchun kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni kuchaytirish	648
B.Sh. Akbarova	
Elektr ta'minoti uzilishlarining xarajatlari va yo'qotishlarini hisobga olish usullarini takomillashtirish	652
Akbar Ashurovich Shodiyev	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini subsidiyalash zaruriyatining ilmiy asoslari.....	656
Valiyev Shamsiddin Eshpulatovich	
“Internal factors influencing the competitiveness of the textile industry”	662
Ikramova Nodira Burkxon kizi	
Raqamli texnologiyalar va ularning inflyatsiya jarayonlariga ta'sirining nazariy asoslari.....	669
Sobirov Baxtiyor	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan valyuta operatsiyalari hisobini takomillashtirish mexanizmlari	674
Akbarov Husniddinjon Mo'ysin o'g'li	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarining eksport salohiyati oshirish masalalari.....	679
To'xtasinov Boburbek Yusufjon o'g'li	
Mintaqada oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmi.....	683
Q.O.Tursunboyev	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda foydaning strategik boshqaruv hisobini tashkil qilish yo'nalishlari	688
Pardayeva Shahnoza Abdinabiyevna	
Kapital bozorida moliyaviy resurslar jalb qilishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	693
Xasanov Xayrullo Nasrullayevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida shubhali soliq to'lovchilarni aniqlash va kamaytirishning metodolik asoslari	699
Axmedov Feruz Baxodirovich	

Yer qa'ridan foydalanganlik uchun soliq mexanizmlarining tahlili.....	708
Anvarov Alisher Xaybulloevich	
Turizmda bandlikni ta'minlashning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	717
Ermetova Iqbol Tajiboyevna	
O'zbekistondagi kichik biznes subyektlarini banklar orqali moliyaviy rag'batlantirishning samaradorligini tahlil qilish va baholash.....	722
Hamroqulov Xushbaxt Sadriddinovich	
Kichik tadbirkorlik subyektlarining hudud eksport salohiyatini oshirishga ta'sirini ekonometrik tadqiqi.....	725
Boymatova Dildora Olim qizi	
Модели финансового механизма воздействия на производство собственной продукции предприятий общественного питания.....	729
Зайналова Камола Нодировна	
Совершенствование системы оказания транспортных услуг субъектам предпринимательства.....	735
Хужаев Фазлиддин Элмуратович	
Yashil iqtisodiyot barqarorligida raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni.....	742
Saidov Muhammad ali Hakimovich, Esanbekov Diyorbek Mirzabek o'g'li	
Ijtimoiy sohalar rivojlanishida davlat budjeti xarajatlarining ahamiyati.....	749
Kurbonov Xayrilla Abdurasulovich, Ramozonov Nodir Mardonovich	
Barqaror rivojlanish konsepsiyasini amalga oshirishda islomiy va ijtimoiy moliyaviy institutlarning roli.....	756
Nazarov Nodirjon Namoz o'g'li	
Kichik tadbirkorlik subyektlari va ularni soliqqa tortish mexanizmiga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar.....	764
Abdullazoda Shukrullo Elmurod o'g'li	
Ilmiy maqolaga zamonaviy talablar (yoki uni IMRAD tuzilmasi bo'yicha yozish).....	770
R.D.Dusmuratov	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida korporativ boshqaruv tizimini samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	778
Mallayev Salohiddin Saidkamolovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda inson kapitalini yangi belgilari va xususiyatlarining shakllanishi va rivojlanishi.....	783
Butaboyev Muhammadjon, Jumaboyev Dilmurod	
Mehnat unumdorligining omilli tahlili hamda uning korxonada moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlariga ta'sirini baholash.....	787
Abdujabborova Ma'mura Toshmuxamadovna	
Sanoat korxonalarini restrukturizatsiyalash zaruriyati.....	792
B. Sulaymonov	
Elektr energiya yo'qotishlarini hisobga olish uslubiyotini takomillashtirish.....	798
Akbar Ashurovich Shodiyev	
"Yashil" obligatsiyalar va investitsiyalar-"yashil" iqtisodiyotni moliyalashtirishning asosiy manbalari.....	803
Raximov To'xtabek Jumaboyevich, Sharipbayev Bobur Marks o'g'li	
Davlat sektori subyektlarida moliyalashtirish manbalari bo'yicha daromadlar hisobini tashkil etish.....	810
Igamberdiyev Sahobiddin Xatam o'g'li	
Raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llash asosida yer resurslarini boshqarish.....	815
Aslonov Azizbek Faxritdin o'g'li	
Региональный туризм в самарканде, анализ проведенных экскурсий и его перспективы развития.....	824
Абидова Дилфуза Игамбердиевна, Абдуллаходжаев. А., Шодиева Ш., Абдуллаходжаева А.Ш.	
Ways of developing branding process in higher educational institutions.....	832
Shakirova Dilfuza Tulkunovna	

WAYS OF DEVELOPING BRANDING PROCESS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Shakirova Dilfuza Tulkunovna

Senior lecturer of the english language department at Tashkent state university of economics

Abstract: Strengthening a brand of the business in order to be distinguished among existing competitors, is under strict supervision of the management nowadays, without paying attention to the form of the company, where assets are of great importance. Each stakeholder of the business should realize the importance of the process, as assets, especially material elements in the structure of the asset are totally combined with delivering brand idea of the company. In the article one of the main concepts of branding brand personality has been discussed in detail as an effective means of communication between company and consumer.

Key words: asset management, intellectual property, brand personality, educational service, education brand.

Annotatsiya: Biznes brendini mustahkamlash va mavjud raqobatchilar orasida ajralib turish hozirgi kunda menejmentning qat'iy nazorati ostida bo'lib, kompaniyaning huquqiy shakliga e'tibor berilmagan holda aktivlarning muhimligi ta'kidlanadi. Biznesning har bir manfaatdori ushbu jarayonning ahamiyatini tushunishi kerak, chunki aktivlar, ayniqsa moddiy elementlar, kompaniyaning brend g'oyasini yetkazish bilan bevosita bog'liq. Ushbu maqolada brendingning asosiy tushunchalaridan biri – brend shaxsiyati kompaniya va iste'molchi o'rtasidagi samarali kommunikatsiya vositasi sifatida batafsil muhokama qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: aktivlarni boshqarish, intellektual mulk, brend shaxsiyati, ta'lim xizmati, ta'lim brendi.

Аннотация: Укрепление бренда бизнеса с целью выделения среди существующих конкурентов находится под строгим контролем менеджмента в настоящее время, независимо от формы компании, где активы имеют большое значение. Каждый заинтересованный субъект бизнеса должен осознавать важность этого процесса, так как активы, особенно материальные элементы, напрямую связаны с передачей идеи бренда компании. В статье подробно рассмотрено одно из ключевых понятий брендинга – личность бренда, как эффективное средство коммуникации между компанией и потребителем.

Ключевые слова: управление активами, интеллектуальная собственность, личность бренда, образовательные услуги, бренд образования.

INTRODUCTION

To stand out in the market and gain recognition from both consumers and investors, every business strives to develop a unique strategy that strengthens its brand. Without a well-defined and effective branding approach, a company risks losing not only its profit and prestige but also its market share. While hiring competent leaders and skilled teams can contribute to brand development, the greater challenge lies in maintaining and reinforcing the brand over the long term. The rapid advancements in information technology and globalization have significantly influenced brand positioning by increasing consumer awareness of similar products and services.

Given the substantial impact of external factors on brand-building, merely employing top-tier specialists is insufficient. A more effective approach involves continuous market monitoring and the development of adaptive strategies to respond to changes. This requires a strong focus on intellectual assets, which have gained increasing importance in recent years. Previously, businesses primarily emphasized tangible assets in their asset structure. However, today, intangible elements such as trademarks, company names, and brand equity are recognized as crucial components of a company's value.

The management of intellectual assets plays a vital role in shaping and executing strategic business decisions. In the past, asset management was largely centered around material resources, but in today's innovation-driven economy, intellectual capital has emerged as a key competitive advantage. Intellectual property assets, including industrial property, trademarks, company names, customer bases, and business reputation, have become fundamental to sustainable growth and market differentiation.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The issue of development tertiary education structure, which certainly influences to the brand of the organization, has been studied by scholars of our country; all these scientific works cover different aspects.

In doctoral dissertation prof. D.Rahmonov justifies the methodology of formation of the amount of education fee depending on the scientific potential¹ and proposes to introduce the practice of public-private partnership as a priority aspect of increasing the volume of extra-budgetary funds in the field of higher education, while N.Zufarova proves in PhD dissertation that in the financial evaluation of the brand capital in the conditions of the formation of the brand of the higher education institution, the expediency of giving priority in the financial balance to foreign students and foreign listeners, sponsorship, extra-budgetary funds received from legal entities and individuals is based on the expediency².

All these attempts try to increase the quality of education service in order to approach world standards, to increase competitive atmosphere and form a strong brand, which certainly serves to expand market share in the sector by satisfying consumers' needs and wants.

As perceived quality refers to students' and graduates' judgments about a higher education institution's overall excellence or superiority (Zeithaml, 1988), where scientific success of HEI and tuition fee paly not the last role; while reputation is the overall value, esteem, and character of a brand as seen or judged by people in general (Chaudhuri, 2002)³.

Each stakeholder pursue own goal in the improvement and future development of their organization, where students care about the quality of courses delivered and influence for job prospective, while professionals' worries are the quality of students who have chosen this HEI to study (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Stakeholders of HEI.

All stakeholders, without prompting, identified the same issues as being critical to the future development of the university. They were:

- The quality of the courses being delivered.
- The quality of the resources, technology and equipment that support the delivery of the courses.
- The quality of the academic staff that design and deliver the courses.
- The quality of the students being accepted onto the courses.
- The quality of the graduates being produced⁴.

As we can see that brand of HEI has different types of constituencies in order to be recognized and to be aware, which creates obstacles and challenges in clarifying perceptions and feeling of all stakeholders.

Philipp A. Rauschnabel and his colleagues developed the University Brand Personality Scale (UBPS) based on qualitative and quantitative research conducted in Germany and the United States. This scale comprises six key dimensions: prestige, sincerity, appeal, liveliness, conscientiousness, and cosmopolitanism. The primary objective of this research was to create a universally applicable scale that can effectively capture the brand personality of universities across different countries.

1 D.A. Rahmonov, Improving the methodological foundations of financing the social sphere in Uzbekistan, T: TSUE, 2018, 72 p

2 N.G.Zufarova, Improving the management of brand capital in higher education, T: TSUE, 2022

3 The role of brand attachment strength in higher education, Charles Dennis, Savvas Papagiannidis, Eleftherios Alamanos, Michael Bourlakis, Journal of Business Research Volume 69, Issue 8, August 2016, Pages 3049-3057

4 <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post>.

From a managerial perspective, UBPS serves as a valuable tool for assessing university brand personality. It provides insights that can help institutions build a strong and desirable brand, ultimately enhancing their ability to attract students, faculty, sponsorships, and alumni support. Moreover, applying this scale can contribute to improving the overall reputation and image of universities, reinforcing their competitive position in the global education sector (Melewar & Akel, 2005).⁵

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to have up-to-date results and information, secondary data has been very effective and useful. That's why in the article methods as observation, abstract-logical thinking, and systematic approach of secondary data have also been used as one of the main methods.

There are several types of collecting data: a) conducting face-to-face interview; b) focusing group discussion; c) conducting computer aided telephonic interview (CATI); d) conducting computer aided web interview (CAWI); e) conducting web surveys and f) conducting mobile surveys. Mobile surveys are becoming very popular nowadays, as almost everybody despite of age and life style use smart phones which affords this type of data collection spread all over the world.

Ordinary least squares (OLS) regression is utilized to look at the hypothesized connections of the article. To extend the inside legitimacy of the results about, different measures of fulfillment, dependability and productivity were inspected at whatever point conceivable.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Enhancing the scientific potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan and positioning it within the global education market plays a crucial role in fostering a competitive academic environment for students, scholars, and professors. To achieve this, it is essential to identify priority areas for systemic reforms in higher education, ensuring the development of highly qualified, independent-thinking professionals equipped with modern knowledge and strong ethical values. Additionally, modernizing higher education, advancing the social sphere, and strengthening economic sectors through cutting-edge educational technologies are critical objectives⁶.

In this context, effective brand policy becomes a fundamental factor in achieving these goals. A strong university brand in an increasingly competitive global landscape can significantly contribute to enhancing institutional reputation, attracting talent, and ensuring sustainable development. Prestigious higher education institutions (HEIs) worldwide demonstrate the impact of strategic brand management on long-term success. For instance, the University of Oxford, one of the world's most renowned academic institutions, has built its legacy over centuries. Although there is no precise founding date, historical records indicate that teaching at Oxford dates back to 1096. Today, it operates through four academic divisions, encompassing various departments, faculties, and research centers, solidifying its position as a global leader in education⁷. When discussing university branding, it is essential to recognize that a university's brand should encapsulate the feelings and perceptions of all its stakeholders, including students, faculty, alumni, and the broader community.

As the education market plays a pivotal role in enhancing a country's competitiveness by cultivating a skilled workforce that contributes to public prosperity, the concept of brand personality becomes increasingly significant. A well-defined brand personality serves as a strategic framework that shapes how people perceive an institution's academic offerings, values, and mission. This, in turn, leads to stronger brand equity, reinforcing the university's reputation and positioning within the market.

Furthermore, brand personality is a key determinant of marketing success, as it influences stakeholder engagement, institutional recognition, and overall attractiveness. In an era of heightened competition in the education sector, a compelling university brand is essential for sustaining growth, attracting top talent, and securing long-term success.⁸ In some cases brand personality is confused with imagery of the brand, here we should remember that imagery deals with tangible profit of the brand, while brand personality intends to creative positive emotional perception of a customer or a segment. Figure illustrates five dimensions of brand personality by Aaker trying to show the attitude of them (Figure 2).

5 Philipp A. Rauschnabel, Nina Krey, Barry J., Babin, Bjoern S. Ivens, Brand management in higher education: The University Brand Personality Scale, *Journal of Business Research*, 2016

6 On approval of the Concept of development of the higher education system of Uzbekistan until 2030, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

7 <https://www.ox.ac.uk/>

8 <https://www.investopedia.com/>

Figure 2. Dimensions of brand personality⁹.

With the rapid advancement of the internet and globalization, organizations are now required to establish a strong presence not only in the physical marketplace but also online. In this digital era, brand personality plays a crucial role in shaping how a company is perceived across various platforms. Regardless of location, a well-established brand should be recognizable and familiar to consumers worldwide—similar to how Apple has built a universally recognized brand identity.

Apple’s brand personality revolves around simplicity, innovation, and user-centric design, aiming to eliminate complexity from people’s lives. This philosophy is reflected in every aspect of the company’s operations, from the design of its stores and the appearance of its staff to the gadgets they use and the customer interactions they foster. Apple prioritizes a humanistic approach, striving to create a genuine emotional connection with its users. Through these qualities, Apple has positioned itself as a customer-centric brand that is not only innovative but also highly supportive in helping individuals and businesses achieve their goals¹⁰.

Speaking about educational services the whole management, faculty and even campus should illustrate the care for their customers, worrying about their convenience in learning process, making it efficient and effective. The practice and knowledge they obtained at the educational institution should serve for their prosperity and prosperity of the society in the future (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Brand Personality and Its Impact on Communication¹¹.

9 Aaker, J. L. (1997). Dimensions of brand personality. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 34(3), 347–356

10 <https://www.outsidethesquare.com/news/brand-personality-how-to-make-your-brand-stand-out-in-the-digital-world/>

11 <https://www.outsidethesquare.com/news/brand-personality-how-to-make-your-brand-stand-out-in-the-digital-world/>

As illustrated in the figure, all efforts are directed toward ensuring that customers are well-informed about a product or service through various communication channels. The advancement of the internet and globalization has had both positive and negative impacts on this process. While it has enabled brands to reach wider audiences, it has also exposed them to greater scrutiny, as consumers now have access to both positive and negative information about a brand. Additionally, misinformation can spread rapidly, sometimes due to fraudulent sources, which may influence consumer perception.

In the higher education sector, understanding the needs and expectations of students, their parents, and experienced faculty members is essential. Digital marketing plays a crucial role in addressing these demands. According to ComboApp, an effective higher education marketing strategy should incorporate the following ten key techniques:

- Branding
- Search Engine Optimization (SEO)
- A Great Website Experience
- Social Media Marketing
- Livestreaming
- Email Marketing
- Interactive Advertising
- Leveraging Alumni and Students
- Distance Learning
- Pay-Per-Click (PPC) Advertising

It is important to note that all these techniques are integrated into digital marketing, as universities must adapt their strategies to align with the evolving digital landscape. This shift not only enhances institutional visibility and engagement but also ensures that educational institutions remain competitive.

From a managerial perspective, implementing these strategies allows universities to assess and refine their brand personality, helping them build a strong and desirable image. This, in turn, contributes to attracting students, faculty, sponsorships, and alumni support, ultimately strengthening the institution's reputation and long-term success.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

For a country to be recognized as an equal partner by the international community and leading global powers, and to compete on equal terms in the global market, it must cultivate a highly skilled and experienced population and leadership. Achieving this requires a robust higher education system that provides students with modern knowledge, strong ethical values, and high-quality instruction from well-qualified faculty.

To meet this objective, governments are prioritizing the modernization of higher education, fostering the development of the social sphere and economic sectors, and integrating advanced educational technologies. One significant step in this process is opening the education sector to private and foreign competitors, which increases competition among public and private higher education institutions (HEIs). This market-driven competition encourages institutions to enhance educational quality, ensuring that students receive superior training and preparation for global challenges.

In this competitive landscape, establishing and strengthening a university brand becomes a key strategic priority. A strong brand ensures long-term institutional success by enhancing recognition, credibility, and market positioning. It also plays a critical role in attracting students and highly qualified faculty, increasing local and international visibility, and expanding market share through customer loyalty and retention. By investing in brand development, universities can secure a sustainable competitive advantage and maintain their reputation for excellence for years to come.

List of used literature

1. D.A. Rahmonov, Improving the methodological foundations of financing the social sphere in Uzbekistan, T: TSUE, 2018, 72 p.
2. Philipp A. Rauschnabel, Nina Krey, Barry J., Babin, Bjoern S. Ivens, Brand management in higher education: The University Brand Personality Scale, Journal of Business Research, 2016.
3. Aaker, J. L. (1997). Dimensions of brand personality. Journal of Marketing Research, 34(3), 347–356.
4. Cliff Wymbs, Digital Marketing: The Time for a New “Academic Major” Has Arrived, Journal of Marketing Education, 33 (1) (2011), pp. 93-106.
5. The role of brand attachment strength in higher education, Charles Dennis, Savvas Papagiannidis, Eleftherios Alamanos, Michael Bourlakis, Journal of Business Research Volume 69, Issue 8, August 2016, Pages 3049-3057.
6. N.G.Zufarova, Improving the management of brand capital in higher education, T: TSUE, 2022.
7. <https://www.ox.ac.uk/>

8. <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post>.
9. <https://www.investopedia.com/>
10. <https://www.outsidethesquare.com/news/brand-personality-how-to-make-your-brand-stand-out-in-the-digital-world/>
11. <https://comboapp.com/higher-education-marketing-agency/higher-education-marketing-strategies>.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 1

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

